

PREVENTION AND CONTROL OF EAR DISEASES BY AYURVEDIC APPROACH**Dr. Sonal S. Patel*¹**¹Lecturer, Department of Shalaky Tantra, RMD Ayurveda Collage Waghaldhara Valsad.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Sonal S. Patel**

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ABSTRACT

Healthy sense organs are a premise of overall health and Ear is one among the sense organs. The ear is most important organ for hearing and balancing a body. *Ayurveda* is an integral and most ancient form of medical system which is primarily aimed at prevention of disease and promotion of health. Its holistic approach towards positive lifestyle creates its inevitable significance in the present scenario. In the present era, increased technology has resulted in change in lifestyle like excessive use of headset, exposure to loud noise, excessive use of electrical device, noise pollution etc which has made the ears more sensitive to many diseases. This can be either hearing disorders or balancing disorders. Which can have an adverse effect on our lives, which remains the most challenging to treat in contemporary science. In *Ayurveda* our *Acharyas* give detailed explanation regarding *karna roga* (ear diseases) and give treatment and prevention of all *karna rogas* also ear care is described under the daily regimen for the prevention of ear disease. There is description of daily regimen like *karnapurana*. In this article an effort is made to control ear diseases and prevention of ear diseases by *ayurvedic* approach.

KEYWORDS: Ear Diseases, Treatment, Daily Regimens, Dos And Dants.**INTRODUCTION**

Ear diseases are those diseases whose occurrence is primarily based on the faulty routine activities, faulty daily food habits and improper ear hygiene. *Shalaky Tantra* is one of the specialized branches of *Ashtang Ayurveda*, which describes the treatment of supraclavicular regions of the body^[1] *Ayurveda* gives a detailed explanation regarding the different diseases of the ear and its management. All the ear diseases are explained under one heading 'Karnarogas' (ear disease). Ear is one among the sense organs. The ear is most important organ for hearing and balancing a body. Various causative factors which are mentioned by ancient *Acharyas* thousands of years ago, are presently the most common cause for EAR disorders, some of which with their correlation to contemporary lifestyle are mentioned here. *Avashyaya* (Exposure to Mist and Snow) - Excessive contact with cold or humid weather is *Avashyaya*. In Present era - Intake of cold items, continuous use of air conditioner and early morning exposure to the mist. *Pratishyaya*- rhinorrhea, *Jalakrida* (Playing in the Water) - *Jalakrida* includes swimming under water, diving, bathing in the river and waterfall,

sea, fountain or sprinkling water. If condition of *Pratishyaya* is not treated or ignored for a longer period of time then diseases like *Apeenasa*, *Badhriya* occur. *Presentera* - Recurrent rhinitis. *Mithyayogena shabdasya* excessive or inappropriate use of *shotrendriya*. Present era - Exposure to loud music, extensive use of the ear phones. Several kinds of ear infections are more serious to health like meningitis etc. *Mithyayogena shashtarasya*- improper use of ear bud or use of sharp instrument for self ear cleaning. So treatment of ear diseases and precaution of ear are more important for health. Hearing loss is one of the commonest disabilities in the world and is often referred to as the hidden disability. The World Health Organisation estimated that in the year 20 there were 278 million people in the world with disabling hearing impairment.

In *ayurveda* our *acharya* described many kinds of treatment for ear diseases like *karnapramarja*, *karnadhoopan*, *karnapurana*, *karnadhavan* etc. In *dincharya* for daily regimen *Acharya* described *karnapurna*. And also described Do's and Don'ts for prevention ear diseases.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Brihatrayi (Charak Samhita, Sushruta Samhita and Astanghrdaya samhita), Laghutrayi (Madhavidan, Bhavprakash and Sharandhar Samhita) with commentaries and other classical texts have been used for this compilation with critical analysis, relevant modern texts, articles from PubMed, google scholars etc were thoroughly searched.

EAR HYGIENE METHODS AND ITS IMPORTANCE

Ayurveda aims first at maintaining a healthy body and preventing ailments by adopting a proper, healthy, life style. To fulfil this aim, in the *Samhita* which includes daily regimes in the form of *Dinacharya*, seasonal regimes in the form of *Ritucharya*, deictic regimes as well as behavioural patterns described under *Swasthavritta*. Explaining the ways of maintaining healthy and preventive measures. Hearing are main important work of ear. Only *Ayurveda* has mentioned *karnatarpan* as a part of *Dinacharya* to keep ear clean and healthy and for treatment purpose *Acharyas* described *kriyakalpas* of *karna*. They are *karnapramarjan*, *karnadhavan*, *karnapooran*, *karnadhoopan*.

Karnatarpan: in *dinacharya* our *acharya* described *karnatarpan*. *Karna tarpan* means put some drop of oil in ear canal.

Use: Nourishment of ear.

Karna pramarjan: simple meaning of *pramarjan* is Cleaning ear. *Karna pramarjana* is the procedure of cleaning the ear (plus discharge, debris) with the help of a cotton or gauze piece. *Pramarjana* is the first treatment for *karna roga* before the application of medicine.

Use: *Vrana shuddi*, *Sheegra vrana ropana*, *karna gutha pramarjan*

Karndhavan or Karna Prakshalana: simple meaning of *dhavan* is toileting of ear. *Karna Prakshalana* is a technique of ear toileting with various liquid drugs like *kwath*, *swarasa* and *oil*. Decoctions like *Surasadi Gana* and *Rajvrikashadi Gana* these drugs are known to be best for cleansing ear^[2]

Use: to wash away pus, debris, Infected discharge, excess wax.

Karnapooran: In simple terms, it is the filling up of each ear - not at the same time - with warm, medicated oil is called *karnapooran*.

Indications(uses) Different diseases related to the ear, head, and cervical spine may be effectively treated by the *Karnapurana*. *Vataja Karnaroga* - Prevents diseases of the vitiated *Vata Dosh* in the ears. *Manyagraha* -Cures stiffness of the sides of the neck. *Hanugraha* - Relieves stiffness of the mandible. *Hanushula* - Effective in

painful mandible. *Manyashula* - Cures pain in the sides of the neck. *Shirashula* - Relieves headache due to different causes. *Karnashula* - Gives spontaneous relief in earache. *Badhirya* - Protects ear from damage and hence a person does not develop deafness.

Contraindications: In the conditions like a perforated tympanic membrane, CSOM, Cholesteatoma *Karnapoorana* should not be performed because it may lead to complications as it is difficult to make complete sterile conditions

Karnadhoopan: *Dhoopan* means fumigation. *Karna dhoppaan* means fumigation given *go karna* with help of *varti* which prepare with different drug like *haridra*, *ghrita*, *guugalu*, *vidang* etc.

Use: Helps to reduce bacterial affection of ear, Increase the blood circulation to the ear, Helps to reduce the ear pain

Indications: • Ear boils • Ear infections • Swimmers ear • Otomycosis • Vestibular neuritis Otitis media

PATHYA AND APATHYA (wholesome and unwholesome) FOR HEALTHY EAR CAVITY

The general regimen to be followed by a person with ear diseases are intake of ghee, meat soup, avoidance of exercise or physical exertion, head bath, following celibacy, avoiding talking.^[3]

PATHYA

- A) *Ahar 1 Drava* - Purana *ghruta*
- 2 *Anna Gehu*, *dhali chaval*, *mudaga*, *Yava*, *Lavka*, *Mayur-Harina*, *titir murga maamsa*, *karvellaka*, *Patola*, *Sahijana*, *Benhgana*, *Punarnava Shaka*, *Sunishnika shaka*
- B) *Vihar*- *Brahmacharya*, *atialpa*
- C) *Aushadh* - *Rasayana sevana*
- D) *Upakrama* - *Swedana*, *Virechana*, *Vaman*, *Nasya*, *Dhumapana* and *Raktamokshana*

Apathya

- A) *Ahar*
- 1 *Drava* - *shital jala*
- 2 *Anna Viruddha* *anna evam pana ka sevana*, *kapha karaka evam guru padartha ka sevana*
- B) *Vihar* - *Vyayama*, *Shirahsnana*, *danta kashta*, *sheeta vayu evam shital jala ka sparsha*^[4]

DISCUSSION

In the present scenario the lifestyle of people is occupied of hectic schedules. Ear disorders are most likely to occur in certain people who does not maintain ear hygiene properly every day. From the forgoing it is clear that thousands of years ago, *Ayurvedic* treatises had very broad knowledge regarding *karnarogas* including its prevention and treatment. The teachings and principles which were put forth in ancient times to keep one's health disease free, the exact same philosophy is implicated in modern times. But to lead a luxurious life

in the present era, money has got precedence, in running after this precedence man has scarcity of time for personal life. This scarcity of time progresses with negligence of health. *Ayurveda's* simplicity, inclination towards natural modalities and a consideration of other causes of an ailment are possibly the best reason explaining its popularity. Changes should be made in diet, behaviour and life style. While adopting the adjustments one can best follow the principles of *Dinacharya* (daily regimen) and *pathya pathya* (dos and don'ts). Few modifications in our daily routine can keep us away from common ear problems. *Ayurveda* is a treasure of herbal formulations and other therapeutic measures, but keeping modern life-style in mind, where man has lack of time for himself, measures which can be easily incorporated in routine are discussed here.

Karnatarpan: *karnatarpan use in daily life it provide nourishment to shotrendriya(ear) Karna.*

Avashyaya (Exposure to Mist and Snow) - Excessive contact with cold or humid weather is Avashyaya, especially during winter season it causes vitiation of both Vata and Kapha Dosha because of its Sheetaava property. After Nidana Sevana, ear which is already vitiated by Vata Dosha leads to increased Kleda Bhava of Mamsa and Rakta which facilitates the growth of Krimi in Karna it further causes Karnashoola.

in Present era - Intake of cold items, continuous use of air conditioner and early morning exposure to the mist. Jalakrida (Playing in the Water) - Jalakrida includes swimming under water, diving, bathing in the river, sea, fountain or sprinkling water. They are Sheeta in property leading to Kapha vitiation. Spending more time in water causes Vata Prakopa also.

The underwater diving may lead to Avarana of Vata in the ear resulting in discharge that is called Karnasrava. Karnashoola can also be seen as a symptom of karnaSrava. Present era - Swimming, water sports, under water diving, By Sevana of Kapha Prakopaka Nidana, accumulated vitiated Kapha dosha in the ear canal produces severe itching sensation and inflammation Acid eructation - with each episode patient complains of itching in both ears. To remove impacted wax, excessive and unwise use of cotton bud is used by some people which cause discomfort, vertigo and conductive hearing loss.

The self-cleaning of ear canal occurs by epithelial migration from tympanic membrane, aided by movements of temporomandibular joint. Sometimes if a sharp instrument like hair pins are used it can also cause injury to external auditory canal or perforation of tympanic membrane which may further lead to otitis externa.^[5] The disease occurs by Vega sandharana, Ajeerna, Raja, Atibhashya, Krodha, Rituvaishmya, Shiroabhitapa, Prajagara, Atiswapna, Ambusheeta, Maithuna, Avashyaya, Dhooma. These factors lead to the

aggravation of Vata Dosha^[5] and other Doshas individually or collectively. If condition of Pratishyaya is not treated or ignored for a longer period of time then diseases like Apeenasa, Badhriya occur. Present era - Recurrent rhinitis. Mithayogenashabdasya excessive or inappropriate use of shotrendriya.

Present era - Exposure to loud music, extensive use of the ear phones Sever kind of ear infection are more Sertorius and reach to brain and produced brain disease which are more serious to health like meningitis ect. So treatment of ear diseased and precuction of ear are more important for health. Hearing loss¹ is one of the commonest disabilities in the world and is often referred to as the hidden disability.

The World Health Organisation estimated that in the year 20there were 278 million people in the world with disabling hearing impairment. In ayurveda our acharya diacribed may kind of treatment for ear disesd like karnapramarja, karnadhoopan, karnapurana, karnadhavan etc. in dincharya for daily regimen acharya discribed karnatarna. And also described Do's and Don'ts foe prevention ear diseases.

CONCLUSION

A few simple regimens like karnatarpan, karnapramarjan, karnadhavan, karnapooraj should be promoted as effective measures for the prevention of lifestyle related ear disorders and maintenance of ear health. Various practices of such simple techniques with appropriate lifestyle modifications along with inclusion of proper diet can prevent ear diseases as is seen in this review.

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